

netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society

Grant Agreement number: 727066

Key Research Questions v2

WP5_ D5.4

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Copyright This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727066

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H2020-SC6-REV-INEQUAL-2016

Grant Agreement number: 727066

1st November 2016 – 30th September 2019

Key Research Questions

WP5 D5.4*

Deliverable description			
Filename	WYRED_WP5 D54		
Type	Report		
Dissemination level	PU		
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.1951868		
Due Date (in months)	M25		
Deliverable contributors			
Version No.	Name, Institution	Role	Last update
1	Early Years – the organisation for young children Northern Ireland	WP5 Leader	30/11/18

* cfr. GA – Annex I Part A – 1.3.2 WT2 – list of deliverable

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1 Introduction

The WYRED project (netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society) (García-Peñalvo, 2016b, 2017, 2018; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016; Griffiths et al., 2017) provides a framework for research in which children and young people can express and explore their perspectives and interests in relation to digital society, and also a platform (García-Holgado & García-Peñalvo, 2018; García-Peñalvo, 2016a; García-Peñalvo & Durán-Escudero, 2017; García-Peñalvo, García-Holgado, Vázquez-Ingelmo, & Seoane-Pardo, 2018) from which they can communicate their perspectives to other stakeholders effectively through innovative engagement processes. WYRED is implementing a generative research cycle (WYRED Consortium, 2017a, 2017b) involving networking, dialogue, participatory research and interpretation phases centred around and driven by children and young people. From this a diverse range of outputs, critical perspectives and other insights are emerging to inform policy and decision-making in relation to children and young people's needs in relation to digital society.

The dialogues' primary focus is to give children and young people (C&YP) the opportunity to share their voice about their thoughts, fears and feelings in relation to the online world through a range of topics and themes that interest and/or concern them.

The Dialogues engendered lively and energetic debate among children and young people and they identified possible research questions/areas of foci under the prioritized Delphi/WYRED themes (Hauptman, Kearney, Raan, & Soffer, 2018; Hauptman & Soffer, 2017) – see table below.

The dialogues facilitated by the 9 WYRED partners provided the opportunities for C&YP to explore both the digital and physical worlds in which they live. The themes identified throughout the Delphi process in Cycle 1 and Cycle 2 provided the stimulus for the later conversations to begin and to grow.

A wide range of potential research areas were identified throughout this process by the partners and this will be explored further.

Below is a summary of the prioritized areas and research activity identified through the dialogues from which research questions were generated.

2 The WYRED Digital Themes and 15 Delphi Themes

WYRED “digital-oriented” themes:	DELPHI 2 Themes:
1. Self-image and its presentation online	1. Self-image, self-confidence
2. Gender discrimination, and gender differences online	2. Tolerance to different cultures/opinions
3. Stereotyping in online contexts	3. Necessary changes in education (e.g. future-oriented)
4. Internet safety	4. Causes of stress among young people
5. Internet privacy	5. Employment prospects
6. Living on social media	6. Cyber-bullying, shaming
7. Access to information, and fake news	7. Internet safety & privacy
8. Media literacy	8. Gender stereotypes / discrimination
9. Cyberbullying and online abuse	9. Integration of migrants/refugees in schools and in the society
10. Digital activism	10. Adult misunderstandings of young people
11. Future of employment in a digital world	11. Reliability of information on the Internet and social media
12. Changes in education in a digital world	12. Roles of parents, friends and peer groups
13. Tolerance of different cultures, and integration of migrants	13. Environmental problems (e.g. pollution)
14. Living with stress online	14. Crime
15. Digital divide	15. Mental wellbeing

3 Key Research Questions - List of suggestions for the research activities arising from the Dialogues by Partner during the 2nd Cycle (July 2017 – October 2018)

BOUNDARIES

Prioritized Topics	Research Activity / Questions
<p>CYCLE 2 –</p> <p>27 Themes discussed From Delphi</p> <p>Education, animal rights, gaming, online life</p> <p>Social media, gender, self-image, online safety, knife crime, economics and personal finance, toxic masculinity, information literacy, youth participation and activism, poverty, climate change, plastics, future of education, future of employment, popular culture</p> <p>Social media, gender, self-image, online safety, information literacy, Brexit and youth participation, environment, education</p>	<p>CYCLE 2</p> <p>Number of newly generated research questions arising from the Social Dialogues</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 40px; height: 20px; margin: 10px auto; text-align: center;">7</div> <p>List of research questions generated by the dialogues.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How do we experience the effects of influencers in our daily lives? 2. How can we help men to be more vulnerable? 3. How can we address gender discrimination online? 4. How can we use digital tools to manage our economic lives? 5. How is it different to live our lives on social media from the experience of our parents? 6. What might the ideal school look like?

	<p>7. How can we change people's attitudes to animal rights through online action</p>
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USAL

Prioritized Topics	Research Activity/Questions
<p>From Cycle 1.5- research questions</p> <p>12 Themes discussed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender stereotypes and discrimination • Emotional education and Internet • Cyberbullying and shaming • Reasons for stress among young people • Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions • Image of self and confidence • Necessary changes in education • Risks and dangers of the Internet and social networks • Internet security and privacy • Reliability of information on the Internet and social networks • Young generation and adults gap 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Does the digital society contribute to improving (or worsening) the perception of gender stereotypes and forms of discrimination based on sex, sexual orientation, gender identity, etc.? 2. Does the Internet help young people build their own emotional image (friendships, love, sexuality, personal relationships), make it difficult or simply change behavior patterns? Do we feel ready to naturally express our emotions in both worlds, digital and real? 3. Has the digital society changed the way this type of behavior occurs? Have they increased, changed, hidden, etc.? 4. Is there a relationship between the things that worry young people and the influence of digital or real social groups? 5. Does the digital society contribute to improve or worsen our vision of others? 6. To what extent do our "real" and "digital" circles of friends, socializing agents, etc. influence us?

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Employment Aspects	<ol style="list-style-type: none">7. To what extent can the digital society improve or worsen future education? What should change in education so that it adapts to the needs and interests of young people?8. Are we aware of the risks of using social networks, both when we publish information about ourselves and others? Do we know where is the border between the freedom of expression, the dignity of the other, the ethical and legal consequences that can be derived from it?9. Do we feel "safe" on the Internet? What value do we give to privacy versus the "need" to build our digital reputation and the right to share the information we want, when we want and with whom we want?10. To what extent do young people trust Internet information? Is it easier to create and manipulate opinions or is it easier to create a free and well-informed opinion?11. Is the digital society, in which young people are undoubtedly more involved than the older generation, a special reason for intergenerational conflict? Are we so different from our parents because we "live" in a digital world or do we have the same needs, simply expressed through different channels of socialization?
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<p>CYCLE 2 - 6 themes discussed</p> <p>5 from Delphi</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Internet safety and privacy2. Cyber bullying/shaming3. Gender stereotypes and discrimination4. Sexting5. Causes of stress among young people6. Emotional education and Internet	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Without emotional education and knowledge of ourselves, are not we also artificial intelligence machines?2. Can communication, advertising, the cultural industry and audiovisual production be changed, eradicating the different canons of beauty, the stereotypes placed on the female role, the reification of women?3. The world is painted in a way that has nothing to do with reality and young people, when they come across this reality, realize that they are not prepared and that creates frustration and stress. How to change the way of proposing the studies, not to see them only as a way to get a job?4. Cyberbullying and sexting have an uncontrollable amplifying effect in social networks. How can we act to prevent or intervene early without waiting for extreme cases?5. Are young people a cheap copy of the new influencers?6. In what way do the technologies influence the personality or the formation of it? Do social networks help to know a person? And to yourself?7. Do young people know DeepWeb? Are they aware of the risks?8. Loss of voluntary and involuntary privacy when we expose our life on the internet. Are we aware of the consequences?
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	<p>9. How does the social and family environment influence the creation of stress situations among young people? Why do we care?</p> <p>10. Are social networks responsible for transmitting a macho message among young people?</p> <p>11. How does the advertising message convey genre stereotypes?</p> <p>12. Do we have a double identity? Are we addicted to the mobile due to our alter ego personality or do we adopt an alter ego personality because of the mobile phone?</p> <p>13. Should we invest more in cybersecurity? What can we do to prevent online identity fraud? Who are the people in charge of digital literacy? Are you able to surf the web safely</p>
	<p>CYCLE 2</p> <p>Number of newly generated research questions arising from the Social Dialogues</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 80px; height: 30px; margin: 10px auto; text-align: center; line-height: 30px;">3</div> <p>List of research questions generated by the dialogues.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Without emotional education and knowledge of ourselves, are not we also artificial intelligence machines? 2. Can communication, advertising, the cultural industry and audiovisual production be changed, eradicating the different canons of beauty, the

	<p>stereotypes placed on the female role, the reification of women?</p> <p>3. The world is painted in a way that has nothing to do with reality and young people, when they come across this reality, realize that they are not prepared and that creates frustration and stress. How to change the way of proposing the studies, not to see them only as a way to get a job?</p>
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DOGA

Prioritized Topics	Research Activity / Questions
<p>From Delphi</p> <p>(cycle 1.5 Jan2018)</p> <p>Diversity?</p> <p>Urban challenges: cosmopolitan cities and air pollution??</p> <p><i>Environment</i></p> <p><i>Environmental issues (e.g. pollution, water consumption)</i></p> <p><i>Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions</i></p> <p><i>Employment prospects</i></p>	<p>CYCLE 1</p> <p>Number of newly generated research questions arising from the Social Dialogues</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 40px; height: 20px; margin: 10px auto; text-align: center;">5</div> <p>List of research questions generated by the dialogues.</p> <p>1.1 Respect Diversity</p> <p>How to accept and respect other cultures?</p> <p>Why is it important to respect diversity in terms of tolerance?</p> <p>1.2 Population changes in the last 10 years as a result of migration by refugees</p>

<p><i>Self-image and self-confidence aspects Sustainable development</i></p> <p><i>Using social media</i></p> <p><i>Internet security</i></p> <p><i>Using visual platforms</i></p> <p><i>Exam anxiety and career planning, Gender-related issues</i></p> <p><i>Digital literacy</i></p> <p><i>Entrepreneurship</i></p>	<p>The perception of the people towards refugees: how can we change misconceptions, what solutions are the to integrate refugees and immigrants in our society.</p> <p>To what extend do refugees impact the GPD and the employment rate of the host countries?</p> <p>1.3 Gender discrimination</p> <p>How badly are women discriminated against, and how can we prevent it?</p> <p>Does society still discriminate against women?</p> <p>1.4 Cosmopolitan City</p> <p>What makes a city 'cosmopolitan', how did it get there?</p> <p>What are its biggest challenges, and how can we address them? Can the history of the city teach us something for its future?</p> <p>1.5 Alternative to air pollution: Algea</p> <p>What causes environmental pollution in a big city? What are the alternative, scientific solutions to pollution?</p> <p>How can we reduce pollution by using natural resources and sustainable resources?</p> <p>How can we promote sustainable energy resources to control pollution?</p>
<p>CYCLE 2</p> <p>MY VOICE MATTERS</p>	<p>CYCLE 2</p> <p>Number of newly generated research questions arising from the Social Dialogues</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 30px; height: 30px; text-align: center; margin: 0 auto;">3</div>

	<p>List of research questions generated by the dialogues.</p> <p>3.1 Take charge of my own future</p> <p>How can young people reach a greater autonomy of decision making, especially in areas that affect their immediate and long-term future?</p> <p>3.2 Acting responsibly</p> <p>What are the responsibilities that young people need to take on if they are to reach a greater level of autonomy? How can we ensure that the basic rights of children and young people are not curtailed at the same time?</p> <p>3.3 Gender equity</p> <p>Are young females facing stronger resistances than their male peers when they are striving for greater autonomy? And if so, how can this be addressed?</p>
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EARLY YEARS

Prioritized Topics	Research Activity / Questions
<p>EARLY YEARS</p> <p>From Cycle 1 – 1.5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self Image and self confidence • Cyber bullying and shaming • Internet safety and privacy 	<p>Self Esteem-How does the Online world affect this?</p> <p>Do Children really understand when they are bullies online?</p> <p>Are children aware of keeping safe online?</p> <p>Why do children tell lies on the internet?</p>

<p>Cycle 2 From Delphi – 3 topics</p> <p>4 topics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fake news • Selfies /online photos • Online safety/cyberbullying • Hacking 	<p>CYCLE 2</p> <p>Number of newly generated research questions arising from the Social Dialogues</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 40px; height: 40px; margin: 10px auto; text-align: center; line-height: 40px;">3</div> <p>List of research questions generated by the dialogues.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Why do people Cyberbully? 2 Why do hackers hack? 3 How do people find out if Fake News is true or false?
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TAU

Prioritized Topics	Research Activity / Questions
<p>From Delphi – 7 out of 10 themes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information society – the role of technology in our life • Socio-cultural cleavages • Economic gaps - employment and education • Refugees and schools • Sustainability and environment 	<p>CYCLE 2</p> <p>Number of newly generated research questions arising from the Social Dialogues</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 40px; height: 40px; margin: 10px auto; text-align: center; line-height: 40px;">6</div>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Segregation versus understanding between Arabs and Jews • Inclusion and gender (stereotypes and discrimination) • Education for tolerance • Government • Robots and employment 	<p>List of research questions generated by the dialogues</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 What will the future look like, from the social and the technological perspective? 2 How will we experience the gender issue in our future? 3 How will we experience inclusion needs in our future? 4 How will we experience the socio-economic gap in our future? 5 How will we experience environment problems in our future? 6 How can our ideas solve these problems?
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MOVES

Prioritized Topics	Research Activity / Questions
<p>From Delphi - Education</p> <p>6 Topics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental Problems • Future Technologies • Stress • Waste of food • Animal care 	<p>CYCLE 2</p> <p>•Number of newly generated research questions arising from the Social Dialogues</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 40px; height: 20px; text-align: center; margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto;">6</div>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education 	<p>List of research questions generated by the dialogues.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Air-pollution and water pollution – what can be done against it? 2 What do digital implants mean to humans? 3 How can stress in school be avoided? What would experts tell us? What are our experiences? 4 What can be done to reduce the waste of food? What should the European Commission do? 5 Why is it so important to take care of animals? Why animal should not be used for experiments. 6 What is the status Quo of our educational system? Does it fit to currents educational needs?
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OXFAM

Prioritized Topics	Research Activity / Questions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From Delphi – Self-perception • Agenda 2030, • globalisation, • self-perception 	<p>CYCLE 2</p> <p>Number of newly generated research questions arising from the Social Dialogues</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 80px; height: 30px; margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto; text-align: center; line-height: 30px;">9</div>

	<p>List of research questions generated by the dialogues.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How have the digital era and the economic crisis revolutionised the relationship between youth and labour market? • Citizens' social and electoral participation • What does democracy mean? • Globalisation. ONG's denounce and photographic evidence • How is Italy seen by other countries? • Sociability and social media: help or condemnation? • 'Youth and communication: University radio case study' • Bullying and cyber bullying: how to stem the phenomenon? • Self-representation on social media: comparing two generations
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YEU

Prioritized Topics	Research Activity / Questions
<p>CYCLE 1</p> <p>Necessary changes in education</p> <p>Gender stereotypes/discrimination</p> <p>Tolerance to different cultures/opinions</p>	<p>CYCLE 1</p> <p>Number of newly generated research questions arising from the Social Dialogues</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 40px; height: 20px; margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto; text-align: center; line-height: 20px;">7</div>

<p>As results from Delphi were not yet ready or disseminated, themes covered were selected based on the interest of participants and the organization's focus and expertise.</p> <p>13 Topics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Engaging with Stakeholders and higher reach out,	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. What is the use of Digital (tools, technology etc) as content in Education?2. Are young people aware of privacy and safety aspect when being online?3. What is the impact of Social Media on building awareness and understanding around gender and gender identities?4. Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions through the eyes of children: how are differences perceived?5. Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions: cultural development - can the virtual/digital tools help? how?6. Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions from an intergenerational perspective: online generation vs. offline generation.7. Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions at school - what's the perception of migrant students and how does the virtual world affect reality on this topic <p>CYCLE 2</p> <p>Number of newly generated research questions arising from the Social Dialogues</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="1203 1809 1342 1888"><tr><td>5</td></tr></table>	5
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - -Safety and privacy, - -Inclusion and Diversity, - -Employment aspects, - -SM, - -Impact on Language, - -Fake news. - Online narratives related to minority communities; - -Economical disadvantaged groups; - -Discrimination of refugees in LGBT community - -Homophobia towards LGBT communities among refugees; - -Bi-communal cooperation - -Topics of gender 	<p>List of research questions generated by the dialogues.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How online narratives affect disadvantaged communities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - *Roma; - *Socioeconomic status; - *Refugees. • Cyberbullying and Online Hate Speech. What can be done to be protected and stop such cases? • Gender online? What is the local realities and how does that reflect online? • Conflicts and Bi-communal cooperation. Can Digital spaces and tools bring people together? • Homophobia online. Is there a solution to raise awareness and protect victims?
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PYE

Prioritized Topics	Research Activity / Questions
<p>From Delphi 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Populist politics • Money and happiness • Travelling 	<p>CYCLE 2</p> <p>Number of newly generated research questions arising from the Social Dialogues</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 80px; height: 30px; margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto; text-align: center; padding: 5px;">15</div>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Living a full and varied life • Food – food miles, cooking and eating together • Lowering legal age to vote • Brexit impact • General election • Authentic feminism • Refugee situation in UK • Empathy through communication and understanding • LGBT rights, same sex marriage • Cannabis – positive and negative effects • Making bad choices • Role of parents 	<p>List of research questions generated by the dialogues.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Housing in Brighton 2. Manual Labourers 3. Gambling 4. Video Violence 5. Music 6. Gender Stereotypes 7. Streetwear from Sweatshops 8. Faces of Brighton - How multicultural is your community? 9. 4am in Brighton 10. Young Smokers 11. How does technology affect children? 12. Loneliness 13. Phishing online 14. Cost of Living 15. Homelessness
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4 Conclusion

The social dialogue phase has provided a unique opportunity for our C&YP to be fully engaged in a process that will put them at the heart of research involving the online world which is part of their everyday lives.

The results and generated research questions from the Social Dialogues for each partner are listed above with partners giving potential research questions aligned with the prioritized themes from Delphi.

The first WYRED Delphi study (Delphi 1) was carried out during May-June 2017, and the results were presented in a report published in September 2017. The second report presents the results of the second Delphi survey among young people (Delphi 2), carried out by the WYRED project during January - March 2018 - see WYRED Second Delphi Study Results Report - Preliminary Draft July 2018

The main objectives of the second study were (1) to re-examine the prioritization of the key areas of interest for young persons based on the results of the first WYRED Delphi, and (2) to elicit opinions of young respondents regarding several alternative future scenarios related to selected issues of concerns

987 young people participated in the Delphi2 survey and it can be seen that there is a rather high consistency between the two surveys re the top-importance issues which are:

- Necessary changes in education.
- Tolerance to different cultures/opinions.
- Mental wellbeing.
- Self-image, self-confidence.

5 Global List of Potential Research Questions

The **58** research questions generated by the partners are grouped below by topic from the 15 Delphi themes for ease of reference

These include questions from Cycle 1 from DOGA, Early Years, USAL, YEU and PYE which were not formulated at the time of the first deliverable report in June 2017

Prioritized Topics from Delphi Results CYCLE 2	Research Activity / Questions Global List CYCLE 2
<p>1. Self-image, self-confidence</p> <p>5 Research questions</p>	<p>OXFAM Self-representation on social media: comparing two generations</p> <p>EARLY YEARS Self Esteem-How does the Online world affect this?</p>

	<p>OXFAM Sociability and social media: help or condemnation?</p> <p>EARLY YEARS Why do children tell lies on the internet?</p> <p>DOGA What are the responsibilities that young people need to take on if they are to reach a greater level of autonomy? How can we ensure that the basic rights of children and young people are not curtailed at the same time?</p>
<p>2. Tolerance to different cultures/opinions</p> <p>6 Research Questions</p>	<p>YEU How online narratives affect disadvantaged communities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Roma; *Socioeconomic status; *Refugees. <p>USAL Does the digital society contribute to improve or worsen our vision of others?</p> <p>YEU Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions through the eyes of children: how are differences perceived?</p> <p>YEU Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions: cultural development - can the virtual/digital tools help? how?</p> <p>YEU Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions from an intergenerational perspective: online generation vs. offline generation.</p> <p>YEU Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions at school - what's the perception of migrant students and how does the virtual world affect reality on this topic</p>
<p>3. Necessary changes in education (e.g. future-oriented)</p> <p>5 Research questions</p>	<p>DOGA How can young people reach a greater autonomy of decision making, especially in areas that affect their immediate and long-term future?</p> <p>MOVES What is the status Quo of our educational system? Does it fit to currents educational needs?</p>

	<p>USAL To what extent can the digital society improve or worsen future education? What should change in education so that it adapts to the needs and interests of young people?</p> <p>YEU What is the use of Digital (tools, technology etc) as content in Education?</p> <p>BOUN What might the ideal school look like?</p>
<p>4. Causes of stress among young people</p> <p>3 research questions</p>	<p>USAL Is there a relationship between the things that worry young people and the influence of digital or real social groups?</p> <p>PYE How does technology affect children?</p> <p>MOVES How can stress in school be avoided? What would experts tell us? What are our experiences</p>
<p>5. Employment prospects</p> <p>6 research questions</p>	<p>USAL The world is painted in a way that has nothing to do with reality and young people, when they come across this reality, realize that they are not prepared and that creates frustration and stress. How to change the way of proposing the studies, not to see them only as a way to get a job?</p> <p>USAL How do young people perceive the future of work? What value do we give to “digital” in our employability possibilities?</p> <p>TAU What will the future look like, from the social and the technological perspective?</p> <p>TAU How will we experience the socio-economic gap in our future?</p> <p>OXFAM How have the digital era and the economic crisis revolutionised the relationship between youth and labour market?</p> <p>BOUN How can we use digital tools to manage our economic live</p>
<p>6. Cyber-bullying, shaming</p>	<p>EARLY YEARS Why do people Cyberbully?</p>

<p>5 research questions</p>	<p>EARLY YEARS Do Children really understand when they are bullies online?</p> <p>OXFAM Bullying and cyber bullying: how to stem the phenomenon?</p> <p>YEU Cyberbullying and Online Hate Speech. What can be done to be protected and stop such cases?</p> <p>YEU Homophobia online. Is there a solution to raise awareness and protect victims?</p>
<p>7. Internet safety & privacy</p> <p>5 research questions</p>	<p>EARLY YEARS Why do people hack?</p> <p>EARLY YEARS Are children aware of keeping safe online?</p> <p>USAL Do we feel "safe" on the Internet? What value do we give to privacy versus the "need" to build our digital reputation and the right to share the information we want, when we want and with whom we want?</p> <p>USAL To what extent do our "real" and "digital" circles of friends, socializing agents, etc. influence us?</p> <p>YEU Are young people aware of privacy and safety aspect when being online?</p>
<p>8. Gender stereotypes / discrimination</p> <p>9 research questions</p>	<p>USAL Can communication, advertising, the cultural industry and audiovisual production be changed, eradicating the different canons of beauty, the stereotypes placed on the female role, the reification of women?</p> <p>DOGA Are young females facing stronger resistances than their male peers when they are striving for greater autonomy? And if so, how can this be addressed?</p> <p>TAU How will we experience the gender issue in our future?</p> <p>YEU Gender online? What is the local realities and how does that reflect online?</p>

	<p>USAL Does the digital society contribute to improving (or worsening) the perception of gender stereotypes and forms of discrimination based on sex, sexual orientation, gender identity, etc.?</p> <p>YEU What is the impact of Social Media on building awareness and understanding around gender and gender identities?</p> <p>PYE Gender Stereotypes</p> <p>BOUN How can we address gender discrimination online?</p> <p>BOUN How can we help men to be more vulnerable?</p>
<p>9. Integration of migrants/refugees in schools and in the society</p> <p>1 research question</p>	<p>TAU How will we experience inclusion needs in our future?</p>
<p>10. Adult misunderstandings of young people</p> <p>1 research question</p>	<p>USAL Is the digital society, in which young people are undoubtedly more involved than the older generation, a special reason for intergenerational conflict? Are we so different from our parents because we "live" in a digital world or do we have the same needs, simply expressed through different channels of socialization?</p>
<p>11. Reliability of information on the Internet and social media</p> <p>4 research questions</p>	<p>EARLY YEARS How do people find out if Fake News is true or false?</p> <p>BOUN How do we experience the effects of influencers in our daily lives?</p> <p>USAL Are we aware of the risks of using social networks, both when we publish information about ourselves and others? Do we know where is the border between the freedom of expression, the dignity of the other, the ethical and legal consequences that can be derived from it?</p> <p>USAL To what extent do young people trust Internet information? Is it easier to create and</p>

	manipulate opinions or is it easier to create a free and well-informed opinion?
<p>12. Roles of parents, friends and peer groups</p> <p>2 research question</p>	<p>USAL To what extent do our "real" and "digital" circles of friends, socializing agents, etc. influence us?</p> <p>BOUN How is it different to live our lives on social media from the experience of our parents?</p>
<p>13. Environmental problems (e.g. pollution)</p> <p>1 research question</p>	<p>TAU How will we experience environment problems in our future?</p>
<p>14. Crime</p> <p>2 research question</p>	<p>YEU Conflicts and Bi-communal cooperation. Can Digital spaces and tools bring people together?</p> <p>PYE Phishing online</p>
<p>15. Mental wellbeing</p> <p>3 research question</p>	<p>USAL Without emotional education and knowledge of ourselves, are not we also artificial intelligence machines?</p> <p>USAL Does the Internet help young people build their own emotional image (friendships, love, sexuality, personal relationships), make it difficult or simply change behaviour patterns? Do we feel ready to naturally express our emotions in both worlds, digital and real?</p> <p>USAL Has the digital society changed the way this type of behaviour occurs? Have they increased, changed, hidden, etc.?</p>

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